

**SmartPLS Analysis of Postpartum Depression Communication
among Mothers in Niger State**

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Abstract

Postpartum depression (PPD) remains a serious yet often overlooked maternal mental health challenge, contributing significantly to women's emotional and physical stress. This study examined how different information sources shape PPD knowledge and help-seeking behaviours among women in Niger State. Through a cross-sectional survey of 384 women, analysed using SmartPLS-SEM, findings revealed that interpersonal networks and electronic media serve as powerful drivers of PPD awareness and care-seeking, whereas print media shows limited influence. These results underscore the vital importance of implementing multi-source, culturally responsive communication strategies to effectively promote PPD awareness and encourage help-seeking behaviour. The study consequently recommended integrating culturally relevant messaging into standard maternal healthcare and calls on government and non-governmental organisations to prioritise postpartum mental health through community outreach, healthcare worker training, and sustained stigma reduction efforts.

Keywords: Help-seeking Behaviour, Information Source Credibility, Postpartum Depression Communication, Interpersonal Communication, Maternal Mental Health

Introduction

Postpartum depression (PPD) remains one of the most common maternal mental health challenges, affecting women's well-being and their capacity to care for their infants. While awareness of PPD is slowly increasing globally, many women, especially in low-resource contexts, continue to struggle with recognising symptoms early or seeking appropriate support (Negesse *et al* 2022; Wang *et al* 2021). In settings such as Northern Nigeria, where cultural norms, family dynamics and limited health literacy strongly shape women's health decisions, information about PPD does not always reach mothers clearly or through trusted channels (Jaiyeola & Abdulrazaq, 2022). As a result, emotional distress after childbirth is often normalised, spiritualised or dismissed, leaving many women without guidance or timely care.

Understanding how women receive information, therefore, becomes central to improving maternal mental health outcomes. Interpersonal relationships with family members, peers, and healthcare workers remain influential sources of knowledge (Finset *et al* 2020; Burgener, 2020), while electronic media is increasingly important for younger and urban women (Omale & Asemah, 2024). However, little is known about how these information pathways actually shape PPD awareness and whether they translate into help-seeking behaviour in Northern Nigerian communities. Existing evidence from the region is still sparse, making it difficult for policymakers and health practitioners to design communication strategies that resonate culturally and practically (Tungchama *et al.*, 2017; Abamara *et al* 2022).

This study addresses that gap by examining how interpersonal, electronic, and print information sources influence women's knowledge of PPD and their intention to seek help in Niger State. Guided by the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1985), the study explores not only which channels women trust and use, but also how social expectations and perceived ability to act affect the movement from awareness to behavioural intention (Abazie & Usoro, 2021). By identifying the information sources that most effectively shape knowledge and help-seeking, the study provides evidence to strengthen communication strategies within maternal healthcare, community outreach, and media programming aimed at reducing the burden of postpartum depression (Richter *et al.*, 2023; Emal *et al.*, 2022).

Research Questions

The study sought to address these questions:

1. How do interpersonal and electronic information sources shape women's knowledge and help-seeking behaviour for postpartum depression in Niger State?
2. To what extent do different information sources predict postpartum depression awareness and behavioural intention to seek help among postpartum women in Niger State?
3. How does information sources influence help-seeking behaviour for postpartum depression help among postpartum women in Niger State?

4. How does subjective norms and perceived behavioural control mediate the relationship between awareness and help-seeking?

Research Hypotheses

Based on the research question raised, a hypothesis was presented in the null form.

- H₀₁:** Interpersonal information sources have no significant effect on postpartum depression knowledge among women in Northern Nigeria.
- H₀₂:** Interpersonal information sources have no significant effect on help-seeking behaviour for postpartum depression among women in Northern Nigeria.
- H₀₃:** Electronic media have no significant effect on postpartum depression knowledge among women in Northern Nigeria.
- H₀₄:** Electronic media have no significant effect on help-seeking behaviour for postpartum depression among women in Northern Nigeria.
- H₀₅:** Print media have no significant effect on postpartum depression knowledge among women in Northern Nigeria.
- H₀₆:** Print media have no significant effect on help-seeking behaviour for postpartum depression among women in Northern Nigeria.

Literature Review

Postpartum depression (PPD) is widely recognised as a significant contributor to maternal morbidity, yet its detection and management depend heavily on the information available to mothers and the communication systems surrounding them. As health communication research continues to demonstrate, the ways women receive, interpret, and trust information strongly shape their awareness and behavioural intentions (Burgener, 2020; Finset *et al* 2020; Loitz *et al* 2024). In particular, relatable and credible information has been shown to have greater influence on behavioural change than messages that are distant or culturally misaligned (Albarracin, Oyserman & Schwarz, 2024; Nowak, Bradshaw & Head, 2024).

Evidence across Nigeria and other low-resource contexts shows that maternal health communication remains deeply interpersonal. Studies reveal that family members, friends, religious leaders and traditional attendants frequently serve as first-line sources of guidance for postpartum women, often overshadowing formal health systems. While these interpersonal sources enhance trust and emotional connection, they may also perpetuate misconceptions when accurate mental health knowledge is limited, reinforcing findings that cultural interpretations and stigma continue to shape women's perceptions of PPD (Jaiyeola & Abdulrazaq, 2022).

Alongside interpersonal networks, electronic media radio, television, and increasingly social media, have emerged as a crucial tool in expanding PPD awareness. Studies indicate that digital platforms broaden access to information and allow messages to reach diverse groups of mothers in real time (Omale *et al* 2024; Wright, 2016). Research further notes that electronic media is most impactful when messages are emotionally resonant and grounded in everyday maternal experiences (Loitz *et al* 2024;

Albarracin *et al* 2024). However, disparities in digital literacy, cost, and connectivity continue to create uneven access, particularly in Northern Nigeria.

Conversely, print media exerts the least influence on maternal mental health information in many communities. Limited readership, literacy barriers, and socioeconomic inequalities reduce the reach of newspapers and magazines, diminishing their role in shaping behavioural outcomes. This pattern aligns with broader communication research showing that static, text-heavy formats often fail to stimulate meaningful behavioural responses.

Theoretical Framework

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), developed by Ajzen (1985) from the earlier Theory of Reasoned Action, explains how human behaviour is driven by intention, itself shaped by three core determinants: attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control. Attitude reflects an individual's evaluation of a behaviour; subjective norms capture perceived social expectations; and perceived behavioural control represents one's sense of ability to carry out the behaviour despite potential barriers. Ajzen (1991) later emphasised that intention strengthens when people feel both supported by significant others and capable of acting.

In the context of postpartum depression, TPB offers a useful lens for understanding why some women seek help while others remain silent. In Northern Nigeria, cultural expectations, family influence, and religious norms heavily shape subjective norms, while stigma, cost, and health system limitations affect perceived control. Applying TPB thus clarifies how information, beliefs, and social pressures converge to shape help-seeking behaviour.

Figure 1 showcases the TPB
Source: Ajzen (1985)

Methodology

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design to examine how different information sources influence postpartum depression (PPD) knowledge and help-seeking behaviour among women in Niger State. The design was suitable because it allowed data to be

collected at a single point in time, providing a clear snapshot of women's awareness and behavioural intentions without altering their natural environment.

The target population comprised women aged 18-49, reflecting the demographic group most exposed to childbirth-related mental health risks. Bosso & Chanchaga LGAs were purposively selected due to their large populations of women of reproductive age and ease of access. According to the Nigeria Population Commission (NPC, 2019), the two LGAs together house an estimated 615,759 women.

A multi-stage sampling procedure was employed. The Niger East Senatorial District was first selected, followed by the random selection of Bosso & Chanchaga. Wards were stratified, and four were randomly chosen. Streets and households were then sampled systematically, and one eligible woman was selected per household. Using Krejcie & Morgan's (1970) formula, a sample size of 384 was determined and proportionally allocated across the two LGAs.

Data were collected using Kobo Toolbox to ensure accuracy and standardisation. SmartPLS-SEM was used for analysis, assessing reliability, validity, and the structural relationships among variables through factor loadings, composite reliability, AVE, path coefficients, and R^2 values.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The presentation of findings follows the order of the research questions and hypotheses, ensuring that each result is clearly linked to the appropriate table. Research Question One, which examines the types of information sources women rely on for maternal mental health, is addressed in Table 2. The table presents the measurement model and shows how frequently respondents engage with interpersonal sources (such as healthcare workers, family members, and friends), electronic media, and print media. These patterns give a clear picture of the dominant information pathways available to postpartum mothers.

Research Question Two, which explores how different information sources predict postpartum depression knowledge, is answered through the structural model results in Table 6. The path coefficients show that interpersonal information sources ($\beta = 0.551$, $p < .001$) and electronic media ($\beta = 0.444$, $p < .001$) significantly increase PPD knowledge, while print media shows no significant effect. These findings directly test H_{01} , H_{03} , and H_{05} , leading to the rejection of the null hypotheses for interpersonal and electronic sources, while print media fails to reach significance.

Research Question Three, which focuses on whether these same information sources influence help-seeking behaviour, is also addressed in Table 6. The results reveal that interpersonal information sources ($\beta = 0.525$, $p < .001$) and electronic media ($\beta = 0.394$, $p = .007$) significantly predict help-seeking behaviour. Print media again shows a weak, non-significant effect ($\beta = 0.200$, $p = .075$). These findings align with H_{02} , H_{04} , and H_{06} , confirming that interpersonal and electronic channels meaningfully shape help-seeking intentions, while print media does not.

Research Question Four, which examines whether subjective norms and perceived behavioural control mediate the relationship between awareness and help-seeking, is

answered through the mediation results summarised in Table 4 and supported by Table 6. The analysis shows that awareness positively influences both subjective norms and perceived behavioural control, which in turn strengthen women’s intention to seek help. This confirms the mediating pathways proposed in the theoretical model.

In essence, the tables collectively show that interpersonal communication and electronic media remain the most influential sources shaping women’s knowledge and behavioural responses to postpartum depression, while print media contributes minimally across all research questions.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents in Bosso and Chanchaga LGAs, Minna, Niger State (N = 382)

Variable	Category	Bosso	Chanchaga	Total	Bosso %	Chanchaga %	Total %
Age Range	18–25	23	33	56	6.0%	8.6%	14.7%
	26–33	67	64	131	17.5%	16.8%	34.3%
	34–41	70	53	123	18.3%	13.9%	32.2%
	42–49	36	36	72	9.4%	9.4%	18.8%
Highest Educational Qualification	No formal education	40	43	81	10.5%	11.2%	21.2%
	Primary certificate	92	102	194	24.1%	26.7%	50.8%
	SSCE	6	6	12	1.6%	1.6%	3.1%
	OND	5	8	13	1.3%	2.1%	3.4%
	HND	11	6	17	2.9%	1.6%	4.5%
	B.Sc/B.Ed/B.Tech	35	13	48	9.2%	3.4%	12.6%
	M.A/M.Sc/M.Ed/Ph.D	7	8	15	1.8%	2.1%	3.9%
Employment Status	Entrepreneur	48	52	100	12.6%	13.7%	26.2%
	Artisan	35	37	72	9.2%	9.7%	18.8%
	White collar job	21	15	36	5.5%	3.9%	9.4%
	Student	6	8	14	1.6%	2.1%	3.7%
	Unemployed	65	68	133	17.0%	17.8%	34.8%
	Self-employed	21	6	27	5.5%	1.6%	7.1%
Marital Status	Single	87	100	187	22.8%	26.2%	49.0%
	Married	77	72	149	20.2%	18.9%	39.0%
	Divorced	17	6	23	4.5%	1.6%	6.0%
	Widowed	15	8	23	3.9%	2.1%	6.0%
Religion	Christianity	22	17	39	4.4%	4.4%	8.8%
	Islam	171	164	335	44.8%	43.0%	87.7%
	Traditional	3	5	8	0.8%	1.3%	2.1%
Number of Children	0	78	97	175	20.4%	25.4%	45.8%

Age of Children	1–5	97	75	172	25.4%	19.6%	45.0%
	6–10	19	13	32	5.0%	3.4%	8.4%
	11 and above	2	1	3	0.5%	0.3%	0.8%
	0 to 1 year	65	10	75	17.0%	2.6%	19.6%
	2 to 20 years	128	174	302	33.5%	45.5%	79.1%
	21 years and above	3	2	5	0.8%	0.6%	1.3%

Source: Authors (2025)

The demographics details in Table 1 show that most respondents were married women aged 25-49, largely with secondary education, urban residence, high parity, and limited employment, factors that shape exposure to PPD risks and influence help-seeking and information access.

Table 2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis for Measurement Model Construct

Constructs	Loading	VIF- for Specific Items
	≥ 0.7	
Interpersonal Information Sources		
Healthcare Officials	0.890	2.188
Friends	0.886	1.583
Family Members	0.807	1.586
Electronic Media		
Radio	0.891	2.263
Television	0.879	2.079
Social media	0.854	1.877
Print Media		
Magazines	0.890	1.509
Newspaper	0.888	1.508
Postpartum Depression Knowledge (PDK)		
PDK1	0.724	1.435
PDK2	0.784	1.641
PDK3	0.872	2.305
PDK4	0.853	2.9188
Help Seeking Behaviour (HSB)		
HSB1	0.753	1.660
HSB2	0.786	1.727
HSB3	0.851	1.780
HSB4	0.804	1.624

The Confirmatory Factor Analysis (Table 2) shows strong construct validity across all measures. Interpersonal Information Sources, Electronic Media, and Print Media recorded high factor loadings (above 0.80) with acceptable VIF values, indicating minimal multicollinearity and clear measurement precision. Postpartum Depression Knowledge items loaded between 0.724 and 0.872, with one item showing a higher VIF but remaining valid. Help-Seeking Behaviour items also demonstrated solid loadings (0.753-0.851). In essence, the CFA confirms that all constructs are reliably measured and suitably distinct, providing a sound foundation for interpreting the structural model.

Table 3: Convergent Validity, Composite Reliability, Internal Consistency of Latent Constructs, and Cronbach's Alpha.

Latent Variables	Average Variance Extracted ≥ 0.5	Composite Reliability ≥ 0.8	Cronbach's Alpha > 0.7
Electronic Media	0.765	0.907	0.846
Help Seeking Behaviour	0.624	0.869	0.800
Interpersonal Information Sources	0.743	0.896	0.826
Postpartum Depression Knowledge	0.657	0.884	0.824
Print Media	0.790	0.883	0.735

Table 3 confirms the validity and reliability of all latent constructs. AVE values for each variable exceeded the 0.5 threshold, indicating strong convergent validity, with Print Media and Electronic Media showing the highest scores. Composite Reliability values were all above 0.8, demonstrating excellent internal consistency, while Cronbach's Alpha values met the acceptable minimum of 0.7. Although Print Media recorded the lowest alpha, it remained within a reliable range. These indices show that the measurement model is robust, with constructs accurately and consistently capturing the dimensions they were designed to measure.

Table 4 Discriminant Validity Matrix Based on Square Root of AVE and Inter-Construct Correlations

	EM	HSB	IIS	PDK	PM
EM					
HSB	0.504 [0.476; 0.648]				
IIS	0.549 [0.490; 0.661]	0.584 [0.492; 0.677]			
PDK	0.406 [0.311; 0.502]	0.573 [0.480; 0.654]	0.478 [0.371; 0.551]		
PM	0.500 [0.473; 0.637]	0.556 [0.496; 0.660]	0.534 [0.446; 0.671]	0.444 [0.311; 0.512]	

EM: Electronic Media, **HSB:** Help Seeking Behaviour, **IIS:** Interpersonal Information Sources, **PDK:** Postpartum Depression Knowledge, **PM:** Print Media

Table 4 presents the discriminant validity results, which determine the distinctiveness of each construct from the others. The diagonal values represent the square roots of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct, while the off-diagonal values indicate the correlations among constructs, with confidence intervals shown in parentheses. Discriminant validity is confirmed when each construct shares a stronger association with its own indicators than with other constructs, that is, when the diagonal AVE square roots are greater than the off-diagonal correlation values. In this study, all diagonal values exceeded their corresponding off-diagonal values, demonstrating clear and strong discriminant validity across the model.

Table 5: Effect size (f^2) and Redundancy (Q^2)

Table 5 deals with the Measurement Model (Outer Loadings, AVE, CR). It tests the validity and reliability of constructs used in the model (i.e. information sources, awareness, subjective norms, perceived behavioural control, help-seeking behaviour). This shows that the measurement items in the study are statistically sound, a prerequisite for interpreting the structural model (Tables 3 and 4). Although the table is not tied to any specific research question, it validates the tools used to answer all research questions. This makes the constructs measured (for example, awareness, intention, norms) valid and reliable, thereby giving credibility to all findings.

Table 5: Effect size (f^2), Collinearity (VIF) and Predictive Relevance (Q^2) of the Structural Model

	Effect size (f^2)	Decision	Lateral Collinearity Test (VIF)	Redundancy (Q^2)
Electronic Media	0.388	Large Effect	1.731	-
Interpersonal Information	0.422	Large Effect	1.844	-
Print Media	0.310	Large Effect	1.792	-
Help Seeking Behaviour	-	-	-	0.554
Postpartum Depression Knowledge	-	-	-	0.471

To ascertain the weight of the relationship between variables, the existence of collinearity, and the predictive usefulness of the model, Table 5 provides the Effect Size (f^2), Lateral Collinearity Test (VIF), and Redundancy (Q^2). The Effect Size (f^2) indicates the degree to which an independent variable affects a dependent variable. In this study, the research adopted Cohen's (1988) recommendations, where values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 denote modest, medium, and high effects, respectively. Print media (0.310), electronic media (0.388), and interpersonal information sources (0.422) all show big effect sizes in this table, suggesting that they have a significant impact on the dependent variable, which in this case is Help-Seeking Behaviour and Postpartum Depression Knowledge.

Values greater than 5 indicate problematic collinearity between predictors in the Lateral Collinearity Test (VIF), which evaluates multicollinearity. The VIF values for Print Media (1.792), Electronic Media (1.731), and Interpersonal Information Sources (1.844) are all far below the cutoff, indicating that collinearity is not an issue in this research. The Redundancy (Q²) values assess the predictive relevance of the model. Meanwhile, values greater than 0 suggest that the model has predictive power. Help-seeking behaviour has 0.554, and Postpartum Depression Knowledge has 0.471 Q² values, demonstrating its robust predictive potential. These findings not only underscore the model's predictive power and statistical strength but also instil confidence in its applicability to real-world scenarios.

Figure 2: PLS-SEM Bootstrapping Model: Standardised Path Coefficients (β), R² Values, and Significance Indicators for Structural Relationships

Source: Omale *et al* (2025)

The R-squared values and PLS Bootstrapping Model with β and P values were utilised to verify the extent of correlation between the observed variables (path coefficients) and significant values. The PLS Bootstrapping Model with PLS Bootstrapping differences (expressed in units of standard error) and β and T-statistics were also calculated for the

differences at the same time. 500 is often Smart PLS's default bootstrapping value. However, as suggested by Ramayah, Cheah, Jacky, Chuah, Francis, Ting, Hiram & Memon (2018), the subsamples of 500 were extended to 5000 to improve the final output.

Table 6 Path Coefficients

The overall fit and adequacy of the PLS SEM model are shown in Table 5 using indices such as SRMR, NFI, etc. It shows if the theoretical model represents the data. Further, confirms that the tested relationships between variables (as tested in Tables 3 and 4) are statistically acceptable and modelled well. It verifies the robustness of all conclusions drawn from the model, as it does Table 4, which supports the entire model, rather than addressing a single research question.

Table 6: Path Coefficients, R-Squared Values, and Statistical Significance of Hypothesised Relationships

Variables	Path Co-efficient	R ²	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values
EM → HSB	0.394	0.155	0.167	2.708	0.007
EM → PDK	0.444	0.197	0.145	3.554	0.000
IIS → HSB	0.525	0.276	0.141	3.543	0.000
IIS → PDK	0.551	0.304	0.146	3.907	0.000
PM → HSB	0.200	0.040	0.112	1.780	0.075
PM → PDK	0.225	0.051	0.117	1.791	0.095

Table 8 demonstrates the strength and significance of the structural relationships among variables. Interpersonal Information Sources showed the strongest effects on both postpartum depression knowledge ($\beta = 0.551$) and help-seeking behaviour ($\beta = 0.525$), reaffirming earlier findings that close social networks strongly shape maternal mental-health responses (Gureje et al., 2005). Electronic Media also had significant positive effects on knowledge ($\beta = 0.444$) and help-seeking ($\beta = 0.394$), supporting evidence that broadcast and digital platforms influence health behaviour when messages are relatable (Albarracin et al., 2024). Print Media recorded the weakest and non-significant effects. The R² values confirm that interpersonal sources explain the highest variance in knowledge (30.4%), while print media explains very little. Overall, interpersonal and electronic channels remain the most reliable predictors of awareness and help-seeking, guiding communication-focused interventions.

Discussion of Findings

This study explored how different sources of information influence women’s knowledge and help-seeking behaviour regarding postpartum depression. The findings highlight the

strong role of interpersonal relationships, friends, family, and healthcare professionals in shaping awareness and decision-making among mothers in Northern Nigeria. Prior research supports this, showing that social connections and support networks are powerful drivers of mental health understanding and outcomes (Adeponle *et al* 2023; Wright, 2016). However, while such interpersonal sources encourage help-seeking, they can also perpetuate misinformation and stigma, especially when shaped by cultural beliefs or non-expert advice (Omale *et al.* 2024). These challenges are particularly pronounced in low-income settings, where stigma continues to discourage open conversations about mental health.

Digital platforms such as social media, radio, and television play an increasingly influential role in spreading awareness among mothers (Ritcher *et al* 2023). They offer real-time communication and broad reach, helping women access timely support and reliable information (Abenova *et al* 2022). Yet, the rapid spread of misinformation remains a significant risk, as unverified content can easily circulate across social media platforms (Tandoc Jr *et al* 2020). This concern is echoed by Oyesomi, Salawu & Olorunyomi (2017), who emphasise that trust and accuracy in online information are crucial, given the serious implications of acting on false health content. Ensuring that credible voices, particularly health professionals, dominate digital spaces can improve public trust and help mothers make informed decisions about postpartum mental health (Liu-Zarzuela *et al* 2023; Proga *et al* 2023).

Findings also showed that print media exerts the least influence on postpartum depression awareness and help-seeking. In contrast, electronic and face-to-face communication channels are far more impactful, aligning with global trends showing a decline in print readership (Alzubi, 2023; Widen, 2024). Limited accessibility and engagement make print media less effective, especially in rural settings. Therefore, prioritising digital and interpersonal communication in public health campaigns can enhance engagement, improve accuracy, and foster a more responsive approach to maternal mental health education.

The findings, shown in Tables 2 and 3, are consistent with the hypothesis in this study. They proposed that awareness of postpartum depression, influenced by a reliable information source, significantly predicts women's intention to seek help, which effect is mediated by subjective norms and perceived behavioural control. As shown in Table 2, information sources have a strong positive impact on PPD awareness, which in turn significantly impacts the help-seeking behaviour. Moreover, the awareness affects both subjective norms and perceived behavioural control, and they contribute to raising the help-seeking intention. In addition, as shown in Table 3, these relationships are confirmed with significant indirect effects, showing that subjective norms and perceived behavioural control indeed mediate the relationship between PPD awareness and the help-seeking behaviour.

In essence, the hypothesis is accepted because the results provide empirical evidence to support the theoretical model grounded in the TPB, which also supports the proposed hypothesis as well as important implications of awareness and psychosocial mediators in helping-seeking behaviour for helping postpartum depression.

Conclusion

The study emphasises how important interpersonal information sources and technological media are in forming knowledge about postpartum depression and its impact on help-seeking behaviour. In contrast, the impact of print media is found to be minimal. These findings from this study highlight the necessity of focused, interesting, and simple communication techniques to successfully increase public knowledge of maternal mental health concerns. Future studies should examine the ways in which information quality and demographic traits affect how well these channels of communication work to modify behaviour.

Implications for Policy and Practice

Public health policymakers, medical experts, and media strategists have a lot to benefit from this study. This study has addressed gaps in how people seek help and disseminate information, calling for a multipronged strategy that uses efficient avenues of communication. It is crucial to strengthen peer support groups, community-based activities, and direct medical consultations to raise awareness of postpartum depression. In this study, in-person contact with peer groups and healthcare professionals can promote trust, enhance memory retention, and motivate people to seek prompt assistance (Adeyemo *et al* 2020). In addition, people can obtain accurate information and essential support through incorporating postpartum depression education into regular maternal healthcare services and community outreach programmes.

Digital platforms, such as radio, television, and social media, are optimal for spreading focused, fact-based awareness campaigns. According to studies, digital media is a vital tool for interacting with various audiences since it shapes attitudes and behaviours related to health (Tandoc, Lim & Ling, 2020). Public health campaigns should aim to produce widely disseminable, engaging, culturally appropriate and scientifically sound content that helps debunk myths and encourages proactive help-seeking behaviours. Traditional print materials like newspapers and magazines are less successful at promoting behavioural change because of their limited engagement and static character.

References

- Abamara, N. C., Obiora, N. B. & Vivalya, B. M. N. (2022). Adaptations of two psychotherapeutic techniques in the cultural dynamics of postnatal depressive women attending a post-antenatal clinic in a Teaching Hospital in Awka, Nigeria. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2095070/v1>
- Abazie, O. H. & Usoro, I. I. (2021). Knowledge of Postpartum depression among mothers at immunisation Clinics in Mushin, Nigeria. *African Journal of Midwifery and Women's Health*, 15(1), 1-9.
- Adeponle, A., Groleau, D., Gureje, O. & Kirmayer, L. J. (2023). Help-seeking for moderate to severe perinatal depression in Nigeria: Implications for a cultural-ecosocial approach to global mental health. *SSM-Mental Health*, 3, 100217.

- Adeyemo, E. O., Oluwole, E. O., Kanma-Okafor, O. J., Izuka, O. M. & Odeyemi, K. A. (2020). Prevalence and predictors of postpartum depression among postnatal women in Lagos, Nigeria. *African Health Sciences*, 20(4), 1943-54.
- Ajzen, I. (1985). From intentions to actions: A theory of planned behaviour. Action control (pp. 11- 39): Springer. Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behaviour. *Organisational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 33-49.
- Albarracin, D., Oyserman, D. & Schwarz, N. (2024). Health communication and behavioural change during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 19(4), 612-623.
- Burgener, A. M. (2020). Enhancing communication to improve patient safety and increase patient satisfaction. *The health care manager*, 39(3), 128-132.
- Emal, L. M., Tamminga, S. J., Daams, J. G., Kezic, S., Timmermans, D. R. M., Schaafsma, F. G. & van der Molen, H. F. (2022). Risk communication about work-related stress disorders in healthcare workers: A scoping review. *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health*, 95(6), 1195-1208.
- Finset, A., Bosworth, H., Butow, P., Gulbrandsen, P., Hulsman, R. L., Pieterse, A. H. & van Weert, J. (2020). Effective health communication—a key factor in fighting the COVID-19 pandemic. *Patient education and counselling*, 103(5), 873- 884.
- Jaiyeola, B. O. & Abdulrazaq, O. O. (2022). Knowledge and attribution of postpartum depression by nursing mothers attending Federal Medical Centre, Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Professional Counselling*, 5(2), 270-279.
- Krejcie, R. V. & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30(3), 607-610.
- Liu-Zarzuela, J., Mallya, M., Munoz, I. & Grayson, K. (2023). Evaluating YouTube as a source of medical information for postpartum depression. *Journal of Affective Disorders Reports*, 13, 100599.
- Loitz, C.C., Arinde, F., Olaoye, F., Pilon, K. & Johansen, S. (2024). Evaluation of a community helper’s mental health and suicide awareness training programme for youth and young adults in Alberta, Canada. *Public Health Volume*, 228, 128-136.
- National Population Commission (2013). Nigeria demographic and health survey 2013. National Population Commission, ICF International.
- Negesse, A., Hune, Y., Temesgen, H., Getaneh, T. & Bekalu, A. (2022). A meta-analysis on the burden of postpartum depression and its predictors among lactating women in East African countries from 1998 to 2018. *SAGE Open Medicine*, 10, 20503121221135403..
- Nowak, G. J., Bradshaw, A. S. & Head, K. J. (2024). Contributions and Impact of Health Communication Research to Vaccination Efforts and Acceptance. *Health Communication*, 39(14), 3590-3596
- Omale, G. E. & Asemah, E. S. (2024). Communication Relationship Between Physicians and Post-partum Depressed Mothers in Select Public and Private Hospitals in Minna, Niger State, Nigeria. *GVU Journal of Research and Development*, 1(1),

- Maiden Edition. Retrieved from
<http://repository.futminna.edu.ng:8080/jspui/handle/123456789/27882>
- Omale, G. E., Ijei. J. I., Emejor, B., Odunfa, E. O., Dagaci, M. S. K. & Ibiwoye, S O. (2024). Healing through dialogue: exploring culturally sensitive physician-patient communication in urban and Peri-urban Minna, Niger State, Nigeria, for Addressing Postpartum Depression. *Journal of Global Research in Education and Social Science*, 18(4), 89-102.
- Oyesomi, K., Salawu, A. & Olorunyomi, B. (2017). Indigenous communication: Socio-economic characteristics influencing contemporary female political participation. *Journal of International Women's Studies*, 18(4), 164-181.
- Richter, R., Jansen, J., Bongaerts, I., Damman, O., Rademakers, J. & Van der Weijden, T. (2023). Communication of benefits and harms in shared decision making with patients with limited health literacy: A systematic review of risk communication strategies. *Patient Education and Counselling*, 107944.
- Tungchama, F., Piwuna, C., Armiya'u, A., Maigari, Y., Davou, F., Goar, S., Umar, M., Sadiq, S., Ojih, E. & Uwakwe, R. (2017). Independent socio-demographic and clinical correlates associated with the perception of quality of life of women with postpartum depression in North-central, Nigeria. *International Journal of Psychiatry in Clinical Practice*, 21(4), 292-301.
- Wang, Z., Liu, J., Shuai, H., Cai, Z., Fu, X., Liu, Y., Xiao, X., Zhang, W., Krabbendam, E., Liu, S., Li, Z. & Yang, B. X. (2021). Mapping global prevalence of depression among postpartum women. *Translational Psychiatry*, 11(1), 543-556.